

The Validity of Big Data: The impact on the grocery industry

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ABSTRACT

Technology has enabled many applications for the grocery industry. One of them is the personal discount-card. A personal discount-card is an example of data generation and appliance. Most grocery organizations that utilize this data are larger franchises, that provide the population with provisions on a daily basis.

To illustrate, one of the biggest retailers in the world serve 50 million customers a week. When data is collected on a population of this size, the amount of data can be considered as 'Big Data'. But that poses the question: how can these organizations verify that the data collected is accurate and representative, and is therefore valid?

This report will aim to fill the knowledge gap on the challenges concerning the validity of data in Big Data Analytics for the grocery industry and will present the impact validity has on Big Data Analytics, to inspire further research in developing possible countermeasures.

Keywords

Grocery Stores, Retail, Data Validity, Big Data, Big Data Analytics, grocery industry

INTRODUCTION

Technology has enabled various data collection methods for the grocery industry like customers being able to wirelessly scan groceries or the use of personal discount cards. Both examples either produce data or are made possible by using data. In this research we will be looking at the data collected by the grocery industry, which is used for predictive analytics or marketing (Bradlow, Gangwar, Kopalle, & Voleti, 2017), primarily focussing on the correctness and validity of the generated data. To illustrate, grocery shopping patterns can be captured and used to

predict customer behavior (Spiess, T'Joens, Dragnea, Spencer, & Philippart, 2014). But what happens if a loyalty card is loaned to a relative or friend? Or even to a customer standing in front of the line? What impact does this have on the reliability of the captured data and on the corresponding customer profile that is generated using this data.

The goal of this research is to determine if the relationship between the validity of data actually has a relevant impact on Big Data Analytics within the grocery industry. And if an impact is present, shine light on what the impact entails for analytics. Using this research, organizations in associated industries can study the utilization within the grocery industry.

Existing literature lacked essential information exclusively relevant to the grocery industry. Research offers relevant coverage of several topics, but is quite scattered and not integrated.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

The grocery industry is one of the leaders within the retail sector that embraces Big Data for their daily operations. For instance, they collect data from the customer loyalty cards to identify sales trends, update their products, and to develop special offers (Groves, P., Kayyali, B., Knott, D., & Kuiken, S. V, 2016). Organizations within the grocery industry not only do this to improve profits, but also to increase customer satisfaction.

The validity of data is therefore important, because for Big Data Analytics to be useful, the analyzed data should be complete, accurate, consistent and must not contain any errors (Andrew Balas, E., Vernon, M., Magrabi, F., Gordon, L. T., & Sexton, J., 2015). When data does not meet these criteria, it may lead to false conclusions. For example, as mentioned in the introduction, data

collected through personal discount-cards can easily contain inaccuracies. This card can be loaned to friends, or even to a person standing in front of the line, which disrupts the developed profile of the card holder.

RESEARCH QUESTION

To answer the question at hand, this paper focuses on the following research question: “How does the validity of data have an impact on Big Data Analytics for the grocery industry?”. This addresses a knowledge gap in the existing literature and can be vital in forming conclusions on the obtained (big) data. In order to answer the research question, we defined two theoretical sub questions that are essential for this subject. Finally, the discussion will cover the findings of the research, its shortcomings and potential future research.

We defined the following sub-questions:

Table 1. Sub-questions

* Theoretical sub-questions	
SQ1	What is Big Data Analytics?
SQ2	When can data be considered valid?

By formulating the sub-questions, we acknowledge what core aspects of the research question were necessary for this research. To examine “how validity has an impact on Big Data Analytics for the grocery industry”. Research will be conducted on what the criteria for valid data are, how important valid data is for the grocery industry to use it in a proper way for their business operations, and how newly obtained data affects the validity. In cohesion with these formulated sub-questions, the term “Big Data Analytics” must be described and analyzed to form valuable conclusions on the acquired results, and to establish a unified definition.

What is Big Data Analytics?

In order to understand what Big Data Analytics is and how this works, first, it is important to describe what Big Data initially is. “Big data is a collection of data sets so large and complex that it becomes difficult to process using on-hand database management tools or traditional data processing applications” (Kumar et al., 2018). The size of this large data set is constantly

increasing in volume.

In the table below (Kaisler, Armour, Espinosa & Money, 2013) explain the different characteristics of Big Data.

Table 2. Big Data Characteristics

<u>Data Volume</u> : ‘Data volume measures the amount of data available to an organization, which does not necessarily have to own all of it as long as it can access it’.
<u>Data Velocity</u> : ‘Data velocity measures the speed of data creation, streaming, and aggregation’.
<u>Data Variety</u> : ‘Data variety is a measure of the richness of the data representation – text, images, video, audio, etc. From an analytic perspective, it is probably the biggest obstacle to effectively using large volumes of data’.
<u>Data Value</u> : ‘Data value measures the usefulness of data in making decisions. It has been noted that the purpose of computing is insight, not numbers’.
<u>Complexity</u> : ‘Complexity measures the degree of interconnectedness and interdependence in Big Data structures’.

Big Data Analytics

Big Data analytics is the process where advanced analytics techniques are applied on one or multiple datasets. This can be utilized to get advantages within the business and competitively. However, the larger the dataset the harder it becomes to analyze and manage these sets for companies and people. In the current situation, companies and people are not just collecting data, but they also want to know the importance of the datasets and use it as a support in their decision making. We can therefore say that Big Data Analytics is “the process of applying algorithms in order to analyze sets of data and extract useful and unknown patterns, relationships and information” (Elgendy & Elragal, 2014).

When can data be considered valid?

According to the article Big Data or Right

Data (Baeza-Yates, R., 2009) a subtle issue is that most of the time when people want to use Big Data, the problem is finding the relevant data inside large data set. Often it is difficult to specifically target this data, since this forces organizations to deal with bias, noise and/or spam. Privacy is also a relevant subject as it deals with legal and ethical restrictions. Other challenges come with the data content and its intrinsic quality, such as redundancy, bias, sparsity, noise, or spam.

According to the article (Braun, M. T., Kuljanin, G., 2015) it is important for Big Data to have ‘construct validity’. Construct validity represents the extent to which a test measures what it is supposed to measure. In other words, it evaluates how well a physical representation (i.e., measurement) relates to the conceptual construct of interest. The first steps towards measuring a construct in a valid manner are to understand the construct of interest and to design a measure that is thought to best represent that construct.

Data can be considered valid if it meets the following four criteria (Andrew Balas et al, 2015). Data must be complete, accurate, consistent and should not contain any errors. In table 3 these integrity issues and their consequences will be discussed.

Table 3. Types of integrity issues regarding Big Data

<p><u>Incompleteness</u>: of data consists of all forms of missing information. In the case of the grocery industry a possible cause for this effect is the customer being unable to be identified. This might happen when the customer forgets to bring their loyalty card. A transaction can therefore not be linked to a customer and there will be data missing in the customer profile.</p>
<p><u>Inaccuracies and inconsistencies</u>: of data develop when irregular behaviour in a shopping pattern occurs. For example: a customer who takes care of their cousins and who does not have children themselves may not buy products like diapers on a regular basis. This irregular behaviour makes it harder for organizations in the grocery industry to estimate shopping patterns for its customers.</p>
<p><u>Errors</u>: in data are any form of false observations. For example: when a customer lends their loyalty card to a friend or relative, the transaction that is recorded to the owner of the loyalty card can not be considered valid because it represents the shopping pattern from another</p>

person.

For the grocery industry, the validity of data can be considered as important because invalid data may lead to false conclusions.

METHODOLOGY

Focus group

In order for this research to be conducted within the relevant sector, we analysed the grocery industry. Almost every supermarket uses data in order to make predictions, but only the top layer of this industry has the resources to access the full capabilities of Big Data Analytics. In order to delimit the research, we only looked at the companies which have more than 10% market share in the Dutch retail market. Together these companies are responsible for a 64% market share (USDA Foreign Agricultural Service, 2017, pp. 1–3). This includes companies with 17.000 (Lidl, 2019, pp. 1–3) to 100.000 (Albert Heijn, 2019, pp. 1–3) employees and a turnover between €3.9 and €13.1 billion (DistriFood Dynamics, 2019, pp. 1–3). This is to generalize our results over a wider spectrum of organizations.

Hypothesis

Before conducting interviews, a hypothesis can be defined on the subject. Since this research will be investigating the impact of validity of data on Big Data Analytics, the assumption is made that there is a correlation present.

This assumption shall be tested, and proven by investigation (Castillo, 2013). The assumption can be defined as the following hypothesis:

Table 3. Research Hypothesis

*	Definition
H0	The validity of data has no apparent impact on Big Data Analytics of organizations in the grocery industry.
H1	The validity of data has an apparent impact on Big Data Analytics of organizations in the grocery industry.

Conceptual model

Using the presented hypothesis, a conceptual model can be defined to further visualize the potential correlation:

Figure 1. Conceptual model

The independent variable ‘Data’ represents the data gathered by a company in the grocery industry. This includes financial, personal(customer) and sales data, in the form of numbers and/or hard facts.

The dependent variable ‘Big Data Analytics’ represents the use of Big Data Analytics by a company in order to interpret the data gathered. The term summarizes methods, models and algorithms used to analyse data.

The moderating variable ‘Validity’ represents the possible impact that validity has on the relationship between Data and Big Data Analytics. Since this research will aim to answer how this moderating variable impacts the relationship, it is represented by a dashed line. This dashed line is used to indicate the relationship tested by the hypothesis.

Information source

Since this research had to be conducted within a limited time frame; clear decisions had to be made on deciding the most viable way of obtaining relevant information towards our research. Alongside the bound timeframe, our research required expertise in Big Data Analytics and the strategic decisions that drive it (LaValle, Steve, et al., 2011).

Two possible options of gathering information would be to *a)* conduct interviews with a sizeable sample of organizations within our target group, or *b)* consult academic experts. Looking close at the two available options, the preferred method is to consult academic experts. The information provided by experts will be more objective, because of their educational intentions. And the information will be more generalizable, since it will be less likely to correspond to a single organisation (Sandelowski, 1998).

For this research, an interview will be conducted with an expert in the field of Big Data

and Management. The experts within these fields are most relevant because both fields either make extensive use of Big Data, or use Big Data to support strategic decision making on management-level. This is required for Big Data analysis (Kwon, Lee, & Shin, 2014). Experts in these fields will be able to give both an accurate and generalizable insight in the use of Big Data Analytics in the grocery industry.

We chose to conduct interviews because it can give us qualitative insights. Because of the unstudied nature of the subject and the provided resources, this research will be designed as an exploratory research (Sekaran, 2016). The aim of this research is quality over quantity, seeing as little information is available from existing literature. Resulting in a reliance on secondary research. With quantitative research we would not be able to get valuable responses.

Interview execution

The interviews consist of a logical buildup towards the goal of the interview; gaining insight into the relationship between validity of data and Big Data Analytics within the grocery industry. At first we tried to identify the relationship Big Data Analytics has with the grocery industry. Then, the interviewee is asked about validity and its role within data and analytics. To ultimately gain insight on the main research question. Last, an example was proposed in which the validity of specified data was comprised. Using this, the expert was challenged to objectively think in lines of the provided example.

In the section ‘Interview Structure’, a more elaborate explanation of the interview’s structure is provided. Each line of question is clarified in more depth.

The interviews are attached as an appendix. Upon investigation of the appendix, each of the questions has a short clarifications, describing the purpose of the question. In the right column the responses can be found, deducted from notes made during the interview (Opdenakker, 2006). These are not direct citations, but have been compiled from the responses and verified by multiple team-members.

Hypothesis testing

After finalizing the interview, the hypothesis can be tested. To retain validity, all interviews had to agree on the same result. Only in total unanimity shall the hypothesis be rejected. This is primarily because of the sample size (Biau, Kernéis, &

Porcher, 2008).

Since our results can be considered open to interpretation an independent party was consulted to evaluate our findings (Morse, Barrett, Mayan, Olson, & Spiers, 2002). To get reliable results, only the output of the interviews was presented. These were evaluated and interpreted independently. The results from this evaluation were later compared to our interpretation. The aim was to minimize the influence of our involvement, which may have changed the data acquired (Bolderston, 2012).

INTERVIEW STRUCTURE

In order to gain insight on the subject at matter, the interview is structured in a certain way. This structure holds four core subjects; 'Familiarity with the subject', 'Big Data Analytics within the grocery industry', 'Validity of Big Data' and 'Example case'.

The interview is conducted with an expert. However, it is important to make sure the interviewee has the required knowledge to answer the questions. The definition of an 'expert' in the current context is: a person having a high level of knowledge (Cambridge Dictionary, 2019), or has a skills based on research, experience or occupation in a field of study. In this case there is a preference for the field of Big Data. Knowing that the interviewee is an expert will result in a more accurate interpretation of the answers to the interview questions.

After determining the interviewee's expertise on the subject, we will try to gain more insight on the use of Big Data Analytics within the grocery industry. This can explain the existence of the dependent variable 'Big Data Analytics' in the conceptual model (Figure 1. Conceptual Model). This led to the following interview question: '*To what extent does Big Data Analytics play a significant role within the grocery industry?*'. This question will be followed by '*Could you provide (an) example(s) of how Big Data Analytics is being used within the grocery industry?*'. The latter will give insight on the participant's general view on Big Data Analytics within the grocery industry. This provides a better understanding of the dependent variable, but also the industry as a whole.

Thirdly, it is important to try to get a better understanding of the relationship between Validity and Big Data. The answers of the interview questions within this area will contribute to a general understanding of this relationship. With the first question we will determine a mutual understanding of 'validity', presented in two

options: 1. '*The quality of something being logically or factually sound; cogent.*', 2. '*The state of something being acceptable according to the law.*'. These statements help conclude which definition is more applicable when it comes to the subject of Big Data. The relationship between Big Data and Validity in general will be further explained through the question: '*To what extent is the validity of Big Data important in general?*'.

Finally, the last part of the interview will unite the sub-areas in order to explain the predicted relationships. The final part starts with a direct question: '*To what extent is the validity of Big Data important for Big Data Analytics for the grocery industry?*'. According to the participants answer, we can determine whether he or she expects a relationship according to the conceptual model. To put the answer of the above to a test, a case will be presented in which a possible compromise on validity is raised. the interview ends with a question about the relevance of the case for an organization, so we can conclude if the general statement counts for specific situations as well.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Familiarity with the subject - The interviewee has an explicit expertise in IT management. Having worked in different continents and experiencing a broad spectrum of different organizations. The interviewee described their familiarity with Big Data Analytics as "very familiar". The interviewee stated that Big Data Analytics is one of their core expertise.

Big Data Analytics within the grocery industry - The interviewee indicated that Big Data Analytics was something that currently plays a moderate role within the grocery industry. According to the interview, the role will mostly depend on the maturity of the IT innovation within an organization. These organizations were said to be progressing quite slowly, which results in only a select group of grocery organizations that fully utilize the technology.

As for examples, the interviewee mentioned a technological innovation that tracks customers and tracks where customers linger inside the store. This would be useful for re-organizing the shop-layout. Another example would be using this Big Data for 'predictive analytics'. This could basically be used to predict the required stock for specific products, based on existing sales records, weather and more variables. Similar technology could be used to get an estimation on the required employee occupation.

Validity of Big Data - The interviewee is convinced that validity of Big Data is undoubtedly

important: it is essential to actually do anything with the gathered data. “Incorrect data is worthless data”. However, the interviewee believed that the level of validity completely depended on the type of analysis. Primarily, cost should be taken into consideration. If the analysis does not have a significant impact, it is not worth the investment to audit and correct the validity of the data. But in general, the interviewee rated validity of high importance.

Example case - After investigating the case, the interviewee quickly pointed towards his remark on the last category, explaining that this is a perfect example of a case in which the cost to take these cases into consideration would outweigh the benefits. According to the interviewee, the relevance of the generated customer profile was not of significant importance to the grocery organization. The interviewee stated that this type of compromise was so irrelevant to the data set, it could be ignored when analysing the data. He stated that this is an example of an ‘outlier’, a fundamental part of Big Data analysis. Outliers are data that deviate from the norm and outlier detection is often compared to “finding a needle in a haystack.” (Hodge, 2014).

DISCUSSION

The expertise of the interviewee aligned perfectly with our research. Both criteria (Big Data and Management) were met and our interviewee had an apparent expertise in both fields. For the criteria of ‘management’, our interviewee was primarily focussed on the management of IT. This fit our research even better, and resulted in a more elaborate insight on how IT plays a role in the management decisions. As for the application of Big Data Analytics within the grocery industry, the interviewee stated that Big Data Analytics currently only plays a moderate role. However, according to Keh (1998), grocery retailers have been heavily innovating and investing in information technology. Even more than in manufacturing or in finance. This could be explained by our primary focus on the Dutch grocery industry, but is still something worth noting.

The interviewee also claims that mainly the mature grocery organizations are moving towards IT innovation and therefore utilizing Big Data. This statement can be supported by existing literature, where a definite relationship can be identified between the maturity and the motion of improving innovation capabilities (Essmann, 2009).

When it comes to the validity of Big Data, we see that, according to the interviewee, validity

plays a significant role in Big Data. This relates to a general understanding. For instance the Facebook Experiment of 2014 (Panger, 2015), states that there is a significant relation between validity and Big Data. Thus, the opinion of the interviewee relates to relevant research.

When examining the outcome of the example case interpretation of the interviewee, it surfaces that this particular example would not be relevant for the case at hand. The personal data plays a relatively small role when taken into account the amount of data that is being analyzed. But when the compromise in validity occurs with a significant amount of (personal) data, so a bigger sample, its role within the Big Data Analytics of the organization in question, could be important. Although, the case focuses on shopping-data. When the case involved medical data of some sort, accuracy would be of higher importance (Rosof, 2012).

Hypothesis testing

Finally, the proposed hypotheses should be reviewed and tested. From the interview with the expert it can be concluded that the utilization of Big Data within the grocery industry is something that depends on the organization. Some organizations will have more sophisticated tooling for analysing the data, while others lack thereof. Both the interview and existing literature shows that this could be explained by maturity of the organization- which has a stimulating effect on the motion of seeking innovation. Therefore the usage of Big Data is not something definite in all organizations within our sample, something not directly anticipated in our research.

To answer the research question “How does the validity of data have an impact on Big Data Analytics for the grocery industry?”, we will turn to the importance of the validity of the data. The interview primarily pointed out the nuance of cases. ‘The importance of accurate data’, ‘the cost of maintaining validity’ and ‘the significance of the analysis’ should be taken into account. These 3 variables generally give a more detailed indication of the role of validity. This proposed approach is more case-based, instead of solely identifying the role by an industry. By looking at each individual application of Big Data Analytics and measuring these three variables, it is possible to identify the importance of data validity.

Because of the nuance in the results from the interview, alongside the limited amount of conducted interviews, we cannot reject H0. We therefore conclude that the validity of data has no

apparent impact on Big Data Analytics of organizations in the grocery industry.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion this research represents a general starting point for mapping the importance of data validity for the purpose of Big Data Analytics within the grocery industry. Unfortunately the research data gathered from interviewing an expert within the field, can in our opinion not give enough insight in order to generalize our outcomings for the whole grocery industry. This is partially due to the unwillingness of top-employees with market-leading companies, to cooperate with the research. This could have given us sufficient data to draw more reliable conclusions on the current situation of the matter at hand. This is a significant shortcoming of this research.

Therefore we would encourage further research on the subject. That would give first-hand insight in validity and its importance to data, directly related to the industry in question. Eventually, the research findings can also be of use for companies within the grocery industry. A survey conducted among grocery industry leaders and analysts, could provide this data. This could give a better understanding of the impact of data validity within Big Data Analytics.

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